
USE OF E-RESOURCES AMONG ECONOMICALLY BACKWARD STUDENTS: A SURVEY

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Abstract:

The present study aims to explore the use of e-resources among economically backward students. A total of 219 samples were selected from various Post-Graduate departments of Tumkur University, Karnataka. The study found that most of the male (63.92%) and (36.07%) female respondents used e-resources. The majority of respondents (94.1%) used e-resources in the library daily. The result shows that 55.7% of respondents used e-newspapers compared to other e-resources. It is very interesting to note that the most of respondents used e-resources to study course materials (84.9%). The notable findings of the study found that 100% of the respondents preferred PDF file format. The respondents were asked to mention the use of various search engines, but it is surprising note that 100% of the respondents used Google. Further, the study reveals that most of the students have a positive attitude towards the use of e-resources.

Keywords: *E-resources, library.*

Introduction:

Education is one of the main sources of human capital formation. Its development brings socio-economic development. It improves political awareness too and moral education increases human value in human beings. Therefore, quality education is of utmost necessary for the development of a nation as well as the entire world. Quality education can make free a nation from a vicious circle of poverty by a hammer of public expenditure on education (Kro, 2017). Dr. S.R Ranganathan has rightly pointed out in his book the five laws of library science that the library is a growing organism. This statement by him is always right for the libraries as they are growing every day in terms of collection, new

services, adoption of technologies, human resources, and various types of collections (Huded & Naikar, 2021).

Electronic information resources pave a new dimension to teaching and learning and have affected education activities, information availability, accessibility, and use in many ways (Bajpai et al. 2016). The information age is one of the terms used to describe the 21st century, an era dominated by the internet, computers, smartphones, and other devices that enable everyone to access the wide array of information available online (Roman et.al, 2020).

Review of Literature:

Kumara & Manjunatha (2019) in their study found that almost all the

students read library sources for the examination (100%) purpose and most of them preferred to read books/periodicals (99.5%). The study reveals that most Dalit students have a positive attitude toward reading library sources. Roman (2020) study found that lack of awareness and technical knowledge hindered the students to use the e-resources resulting in a low level of utilization. Findings also found that library users are familiar with online resources but are not aware of the online and electronic resources provided at the university library. Singh (2016) in his study states that a majority of the students were using e-resources daily and using the e-resources mainly from the college library, while a few of the students accessed e-resources from their hostels. It further shows that e-journals and e-newspapers are the most popular forms of e-resources used by students. While majorities of the students find e-resources valuable, more than half of the users are facing problems accessing e-resources due to slow internet connections, lack of an adequate number of computers, and frequent power cuts.

Kumara et.al (2019), conducted a study and found that most of the respondents read books at home (69.1%). The study found that most of the respondents have a positive opinion on the use of e-sources than print sources. Most

of the respondents opined that e-sources are cheaper than print sources, through electronic sources the information is available 24/7, e-sources provide voluminous information and they are easy to carry.

The Objectives of the Study:

1. To know the use of e-resources by economically backward students.
2. To know the preferred place of use of e-resources by the economically backward students.
3. To know the frequency of use of e-resources spent in the use of e-resources by economically backward students.
4. To know the purpose of the use of e-resources by economically backward students.

Methodology:

The purpose of the present study is to investigate the use of library e-resources among economically backward students. A structured questionnaire was designed to elicit the opinion of postgraduate students. Samples of 219 economically backward postgraduate students are selected from the various postgraduate departments at Tumkur University, Karnataka. The collected data has been analyzed using SPSS (Version 26.0) and presented in the form of tables.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Table-1: Gender-wise distribution of respondents

Respondents		Total
Male	Female	
140 (63.92%)	79 (36.07)	219

The respondents were asked about their use of e-resources and it can be seen from the table-1 that all the male (63.92%)

and (36.07%) female respondents used e-resources respectively.

Table-2: Place of use of e-resources

Place of use	Respondents	Percentage
Library	206	94.1
Department/Computer Lab	116	53
Cyber café	21	9.6
University Campus	109	49.8
Hostel	28	12.8

The place where students used e-resources is presented in the table-2. It reveals that the majority of respondents (94.1%) used e-resources in the library followed by Department/Computer Lab

(53%), and the University campus (49.8%). The result of the study also found that only 9.6% of the respondents used e-resources in Cyber Café and Hostel (12.8%) respectively.

Table-3: Time spent on the use of e-resources

Frequency	Respondents	Percentage
Less than 1 hour	29	13.2
1-2 hours	150	68.5
2-3 hours	39	17.8
More than 3 hours	1	0.5
Total	219	100

Time spent in the use of e-resources shows in the table-3. It can be seen from the table that the majority (68.5%) of the respondents spent 1-2 hours to use e-resources followed by 2-3 hours

(17.8%) and less than one hour (13.2). Further analysis shows that only 0.5% of the respondents spent less than one-hour using e-resources.

Table-4: Frequency of use of e-resources

Frequency	Respondents	Percentage
Daily	136	62.1
Once a week	20	9.1
As and when needed	27	12.3
Rarely	36	16.4
Total	219	100

The study also attempted to find out the frequency of the use of e-resources by the respondents. Table-4 reveals that the majority (62.1%) of the respondents used e-resources daily, while

16.4% of respondents use e-resources rarely. It is also clear from the above table that only 9.1% of respondents used it once a week.

Table-5: Types of e-resources

E-resources	Always	Often	Some times	Rarely	Never
E-Journals	53 (24.2%)	88 (40.2%)	34 (15.5%)	27 (12.3%)	17 (7.8%)
E-Books	106 (48.4%)	21 (9.6%)	47 (21.5%)	28 (12.8%)	17 (7.8%)
E-Contents/Internet resources	96 (43.8%)	37 (16.9%)	85 (38.8%)	1 (0.5%)	-
Databases	29 (13.2%)	65 (29.7%)	88 (40.2%)	20 (9.1%)	17 (7.8%)
Thesis/Dissertation	1 (0.5%)	19 (8.7%)	161 (73.5%)	21 (9.6%)	17 (7.8%)
E-Newspapers/E-Magazines	122 (55.7%)	70 (32%)	27 (12.3%)	-	-
E-Research Reports	2 (0.9)	38 (17.4%)	71 (38.4%)	71 (38.4%)	37 (16.9%)

Note: The number given in parenthesis represents the percentage

The total number is more than 100 percent because of multiple choice questions

The respondents were asked to mention the type of use of e-resources and it can be seen from the table-5 that the majority (55.7%) of respondents used e-newspapers always followed by e-books (48.4%), e-contents/Internet resources (43.8%). It also can be seen from the table that 40.2% of respondents often used e-

journals and databases (29.7%). The result of the study also found that 73.5% of respondents sometimes used theses/dissertations and 38.4% of the respondents rarely used e-research reports while only 7.8% of respondents equally never used e-journals, e-books, databases, and theses/dissertations.

Table-6: Purpose of use of e-resources

Purpose	Respondents	Percentage
To know the latest information on a subject of interest	172	78.5
For research work/project work	115	51.51
Keeping abreast with new development	150	68.5
To access information faster and easier	102	46.6
To study course materials	186	84.9
For getting information for academic purposes	180	82.2
For career opportunities and development	139	63.5

Students were requested to declare the purpose of their use of e-resources (Table 6). It is very interesting to note that the majority of respondents used e-resources to study course materials (84.9%) followed by for getting information for academic purposes

(82.2%) and to know the latest information on the subject of interest (78.5%) while a lower percentage of respondents used to access information faster and Easier (46.61) and for Career opportunities and development (51.51) respectively.

Table-7: Preferred file format to use of e-resources

File formats	Respondents	Percentage
PDF	219	100
Image	46	21
HTML/XML	29	13.2
Word/Doc	99	45.2
Audio-Visual	20	9.1

The result of the study indicates that the preferred file format to use e-resources (table-7). It is surprised to, note that, the study found 100% of the respondents preferred PDF file format and

Word/Doc (45.2%) file format respectively. The result of the study found that only 9.1% of respondents preferred the Audio-Visual file format while HTML/XML 13.2% respectively.

Table-8: Use of search engines to access e-Resources

Search engines	Respondents	Percentage
Google	219	100
Yahoo	122	55.7
MSN	28	12.8
Bing	28	12.8

The respondents were asked to mention the use of various search engines, but it is surprisingly noted that 100% of the respondents used Google (Table-8). The table also reveals that 55.7% of respondents used Yahoo and an equal

(12.8%) of respondents used MSN and Bing search engines respectively. It can be seen from the result of the study that Google is the best search engine as compared to others.

Table-9: Problems faced in the use of e-resources

Problems	Respondents	Percentage
Lack of computer in library/Department	197	90
Lack of awareness about e-resources	132	60.3
Lack of guidance regarding availability of E-resources	129	58.9
Slow internet connections	107	48.9
Lack of time to access the e-resources	95	43.4
Only a limited number of e-resources are available	152	69.4
Difficulty in finding relevant information	114	52.1
No Training program	172	78.5
Searching and retrieving is time-consuming	116	53

The table-9 depicts the problems faced by the respondents in the use of e-resources. The data presented in the table that lack of computers in

library/department was the major problem faced by the respondents (90%), followed by no Training program (78.5%), only a limited number of e-resources available

(69.4%), Lack of awareness about e-resources (60.3%) and Lack of guidance

regarding availability of e-resources (58.9%).

Table-10: Expectation of respondents in the use of e-resources

Expectations	Respondents	Percentage
Increase Bandwidth	182	83.1
Provision of more computers	208	95
Conduct awareness and training program	191	87.2
Provide a conducive environment	157	71.7
Have stable electrical backup	119	54.3
Subscribe more E-Resources	172	78.5
Provide Training Program	218	99.5

The respondents were asked to mention their expectations in the use of e-resources and it can be seen from the table-10. It shows that the majority (99.5%) of respondents indicated that to provide training program followed by provision of more computers (95%) respectively. The findings of the study also indicated that 87.2% of the respondents

responded to conduct awareness and training program followed by Increase Bandwidth (83.1%), subscribe more e-Resources (78.5%) and provide a conducive environment (71.7%). The table also shows that only 54.3% of the respondents indicated to have stable electrical backup.

Discussion and Conclusion:

The present study also deals with the use of e-resources among economically backward students of Tumkur University. Firstly, the results of the study have given a platform to understand the behavior of economically backward students in using the e-resources which further guides the library to identify the status of the use of its collection. The study also recommends the steps to increase the use of e-resources as well as the measures to be taken to improve information literacy skills among economically backward.

Secondly, the present study shows that most of the respondents are male (63.92%) and most of the respondents used e-newspapers (55.7%) compared to other e-resources. In, this context, the study recommended that, librarians and other library staff should encourage students to

use e-resources more for their academic progress.

Further, the study shows that, the problems faced by the respondents in the use of e-resources. In this context, the study recommended that, university authority, librarian and library staff to conduct more awareness and training programs, taking necessary steps to increase internet bandwidth, subscribes more number of e-resources and providing continuous power system so that students' studies are not disturbed.

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